

BASIC PRINCIPLES ADAPTATION OF ARCHITECTURAL MONUMENTS OF UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract. *The article highlights the current socio-economic and artistic tasks of modern urban planning in Uzbekistan, the involvement of the object of cultural heritage in modern life while maintaining technical, sanitary, hygienic and aesthetic requirements for the reconstructed environment.*

Keywords: *Architectural monuments, historical and architectural cultural heritage, folk culture, adaptation, traditional dwelling, museum, niche, interior, use.*

The more durable the materials used in architectural works, the more permanent and lasting their effect. These works either arouse pride in their contemporaries and delight the next generations, showing the achievements of their time, or hurting them with their appearance. Architectural monuments of Uzbekistan are one of the manifestations of the centuries-old culture of the people, arising from the need to satisfy the practical needs and requirements of people during the beginning of the development of human society.

Maintaining the uniqueness of historically formed residential areas is one of the important problems that concern humanity. Now there is a risk of losing the architectural image of many ancient city centers. The modern use of architectural monuments is of serious importance in solving this problem. The long existence of a historical –architectural structure depends on its correct exploitation [1].

One of the most relevant social and economic and artistic tasks of the modern urban development of Uzbekistan is the protection and use of historical and architectural heritage in the reconstruction of the cities that have arisen. This reconstruction implies not only the physical preservation of individual fragments of a historical building or architectural monument, but also the involvement of them in modern life, while maintaining all social, technical, sanitary-hygienic and aesthetic requirements in relation to the reconstructing environment [2].

Among the objects of cultural heritage there are attractions that are very popular. For example, the House-Museum of Sadriddin Ayniy, located in Samarkand. Dedicated to the life and work of the famous Tajik and Uzbek writer, translator and literary critic Sadriddin Ayni. Ayniy lived in this house from 1917 until the early 50s of the last century. The House-Museum remains in operation to this day. The museum operates daily from 9:00 to 20: 00.

The former home of Sadriddin Ayni is located in the Old City Center, on Registan Street, near Registan Square and ensemble, Amir Temur mausoleum. Behind the road, opposite the house, is the “Garden Of Poets” Square and Secondary School No. 2 named after Mirzo Ulugbek. In this house, Sadriddin Ayniy lived in hiding from the persecution of the Emir of Bukhara, Said Olimkhan, in 1917. In general, Ayniy lived in this house for almost 35 years, until the beginning of the 50s. The house is divided into two parts, the first part was built at the end of the XVIII century at the beginning of the XIX century, and the second part was built in the 1930s by Ayniy himself and his friends [3].

Figure 1. Registon Street 76. House-Museum of Sadriiddin Ayniy.

The House-Museum preserves Sadriiddin Ayniy's living rooms and two study rooms. It was in this house that he wrote his own works, such as: "Odina", "Old school", "Slaves", "Yatim", "The revolt of Muqanna" and other works that brought him fame among Tajik and Uzbek writers and literati. In the house-museum we can see objects, furniture and objects from the pre-revolutionary and Soviet times, the writer's personal belongings, the desktop. In the corner of one room, called "embossed" (patterned, painted), there are winter-warming sandals. In the adjacent rest room, he hosted guests such as Gafur Ghulam, Abdurauf Fitrat, Hamza Hakimzoda Niyazi, Abdullo Ghani, Mirtemir, Usman Nasir, Hamid Olimjan and other prominent poets and writers, and they stayed overnight from time to time. In the courtyard of the house grow trees planted by Ayniy himself: two apple trees (the writer's favorite fruit), a peach tree and grapes.

Figure 2. The workshop of the House of Sadriiddin Ayniy

The use of architectural monuments, their inclusion in the living fabric of the modern city, is of great economic importance in addition to the listed aspects. The building, the restoration of engineering networks, including expensive repair work, of course, is much cheaper than new construction. The other side of the issue is the high aesthetic quality inherent in architectural monuments, their importance of deep familiarity that attracts people [4].

Conclusion. Naturally, a special intense development of tourism is observed precisely in the accumulated zones of architectural monuments. Monument-buildings can be successfully used at the same time at the expense of the development of domestic and foreign tourism, which has brought a significant income to the state and preserved. The problem has in common.

First of all, the tasks of the first level are solved – the urban planning aspect of the problem of adapting architectural monuments for use in the urban system is considered. It is the historical-architectural, morphological analysis of the structure of the city, the designation of the zone of influence of monuments-buildings, the identification of urban planning dominants, the historical core and the determination of the principles of spatial organization of the entire city in integrity.

The main requirement for adaptation - maximum preservation of memorial architecture - in addition to the physical preservation of the building (structures, planiroovka) implies the preservation of its artistic image, exterior and interior.

The following style of design is permissible: the most important requirements when working on the master plan, architectural planning solution, interiors, furniture and equipment:

Maximum preservation of architectural monument.

Individual approach to the adaptation of each specific monument.

The study of the history of the formation of a monument is more characteristic of the architectural-artistic tasks of the moment of its development, whether it is to determine its initial function or not.

The convergence of historically generated and new tasks.

Determining and highlighting the features of the architecture of the monument in the design of the adaptation for modern tasks.

Economic justification of adaptation to the use of the moment.

Creating a high level of comfort of all adapted rooms, applying modern principles of interior design (technicality, comfort, functional zoning).

The use of the principle of belonging to one region or another in the solution of the interior and its thematic organizational structure.

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